

Work Motivation and Organizational Culture as Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction of Library Personnel in Private Universities in South Western Nigeria

Yemisi S. ADEYEYE

Obafemi Awolowo University

Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

yemadeyeye18@gmail.com

Abstract

The study examined work motivation and organizational culture as factors influencing job satisfaction among library personnel in private Universities in South Western Nigeria. The questionnaire was used to elicit information from respondents. All library personnel in the study areas were involved. One hundred and seventy-seven (177) male and female respondents who were library personnel in the South-West were used for the study. Frequency distributions and standard deviation were also used to analyze the data. Multivariate analysis was done with the use of a regression test. One hundred and fifty (84.8%) of the questionnaires were returned and were used for data analysis, showing that (53.5%) were males while (46.7%) were females. The regression analysis revealed a significant relationship between the following: I. Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction II. Organizational Culture and job satisfaction. Also, it was further revealed that the combination of the above (2) independent variables has a significant relationship with job satisfaction. The study recommended that work motivation and organizational culture are factors to be considered to improve job satisfaction in private universities in South Western Nigeria. The study recommended that priority should be given to work motivation and organizational culture in designing intervention programmes to enhance job satisfaction among library personnel in South Western Nigeria.

Keywords: Work motivation, organizational culture, job satisfaction, library personnel, private Universities.

Introduction

University libraries are crucial components of educational institutions, often regarded as the heart of modern higher education. They play a fundamental role in furthering the education of already educated individuals. Beyond serving as repositories of knowledge and experience, well-equipped libraries represent the cultural heritage of humanity, encompassing ancient, medieval, and modern eras. Consequently, university libraries are indispensable assets supporting universities' instructional programs. University libraries are instrumental in promoting lifelong learning and critical thinking skills among students. They offer various services, including information literacy programs, research assistance, and workshops to enhance students' ability to navigate the vast information landscape effectively. By doing so, libraries contribute significantly to developing independent, resourceful, and informed individuals capable of making meaningful contributions to society.

Job satisfaction is described as an individual's internal attitude toward their work, often tied to feelings of achievement, whether qualitative or quantitative. This notion is intricate and multifaceted, as contemporary scholars describe it as a complex construct measured by an employee's overall attitude toward their job—either satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Judge et al., 2017). Various elements comprise job satisfaction, including satisfaction with the nature of work, autonomy, rewards like pay and recognition, interpersonal dynamics, organizational

context, and individual differences in motivation and values (Warr & Inceoglu, 2018; Parker et al., 2017). Job satisfaction reflects an employee's holistic assessment of their job, involving emotions, behaviours, and attitudes toward their work experience (Van der Voet et al., 2016). This topic is extensively studied in industrial organizational psychology and is closely tied to significant job outcomes such as attitudinal variables, absenteeism, turnover, and performance. Understanding the complexities of job satisfaction among library personnel in private universities is crucial for enhancing organizational effectiveness and employee well-being.

Motivation acts as a driving force, inspiring employees like librarians, without force. It involves giving people a reason to do tasks, positively or negatively affecting their actions. Disregarding the ability to motivate employees at work is like denying the presence of influential leaders and effective managers, implying motivation is unreachable. Proficient managers utilize motivation to encourage average individuals to reach shared objectives in diverse fields. Herzberg, along with his associates, proposed a seminal and contentious theory of job satisfaction in 1959. While not directly addressing motivation, Herzberg sought to comprehend the underlying causes of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction among people, including library personnel. Their theory, known as the two-factor or motivator-hygiene theory, hinges on two fundamental human needs: the need to avoid pain and the need to grow. This psychological perspective underscores the dual set of factors shaping employee behavior in the workplace. Hygiene factors, such as working conditions, organizational policies, and interpersonal relations, prevent dissatisfaction but do not inherently motivate. Conversely, motivators, encompassing achievements, recognition, responsibility, and growth opportunities, address higher-level needs and contribute to job satisfaction or dissatisfaction (De Gieter et al., 2018; Schaufeli, 2018). Herzberg contends that not all jobs can be enriched to foster job satisfaction; instead, the emphasis lies in providing the right work environment. The crux of Herzberg's theory is that hygiene factors prevent dissatisfaction and pain, whereas motivators facilitate growth towards self-actualization. This nuanced understanding of work motivation underscores the importance of creating conducive environments that nurture employees' intrinsic motivations and foster personal and professional development.

Organizational culture encompasses the deeply ingrained beliefs and values within an institution, shaping the attitudes and behaviors of its staff over time. The alignment of administrators' relational behaviors with organizational objectives can significantly impact employee job satisfaction. Understanding the interplay between organizational cultures, leadership behavior, and employee satisfaction is crucial for fostering a positive work environment (Kahn et al., 2019). In the realm of human resource literature, several variables are identified as influential factors affecting employee performance. Contemporary researchers highlight job and agency characteristics, attitudes towards merit pay, organizational trust and commitment, the significance of monetary rewards, the linkage between pay and performance, and the fairness of pay systems as key factors influencing performance outcomes (Posthuma et al., 2018; Gupta & Shaw, 2018). Factors such as job satisfaction and motivation are essential in analyzing employee productivity at the time of hiring. Overall organizational commitment is a critical aspect for enhancing organizational productivity and performance. Strategic approaches to managing employee performance, such as the design of incentive programs that address organizational commitment alongside performance targets, are advocated. These incentives may focus on short-term goals aimed at driving employee behavior towards specific productivity outcomes (Aguinis et al., 2016). Efforts aimed at understanding correlates of pay satisfaction have emphasized the diverse individual and organizational values at play. By recognizing and addressing these values, organizations can better align their incentive structures with employee motivations and organizational objectives. Ultimately, fostering a supportive organizational culture that values employee satisfaction and commitment is

essential for promoting productivity and achieving long-term success in private university library settings.

While studies have examined job satisfaction among library personnel, few have explored the combined influence of work motivation and organizational culture in the Nigerian context. This research addresses this gap by investigating how these factors influence job satisfaction in private university libraries of South-Western Nigeria. Previous research has often focused on isolated elements of job satisfaction, such as pay, work conditions, or individual motivation, without considering the complex interplay between organizational culture and motivation. By understanding these relationships, we can develop strategies to enhance library staff motivation, improve organizational culture, and ultimately, contribute to a more satisfied and productive library workforce. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, along with the underlying organizational culture, impact job satisfaction among library personnel. The findings will offer insights into creating a supportive work environment that fosters employee well-being and drives higher performance, addressing a critical need in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria.

Objectives

1. To assess the level of job satisfaction and work motivation among library personnel in private universities in southwestern Nigeria.
2. To examine the organizational culture among library personnel in southwestern Nigeria.
3. To investigate the relationships among work motivation, organizational culture, and job satisfaction, and determine their combined impact on the job satisfaction of library personnel in southwestern Nigeria.

Hypothesis

The hypotheses formulated and tested at the significance level of $P < 0.05$, at $P=0.97$ are as follows:

1. Among library personnel in Southwestern Nigeria, there is no significant correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction.
2. Among library personnel in Southwestern Nigeria, there is no significant correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction.
3. A combination of work motivation and organizational culture does not have a significant influence on the job satisfaction of library personnel in southwestern Nigeria.

Literature Review

Job satisfaction among employees, particularly in private universities, has been a subject of interest among researchers. Recent studies have continued to explore this topic, emphasizing its significance for both individual well-being and organizational effectiveness. For instance, Landry (2020) discovered a positive correlation between overall life satisfaction and job satisfaction among librarians in public libraries. This relationship is significant as individuals

spend a substantial portion of their time at work, and their feelings about their jobs can influence their overall well-being. Judge and Watanabe (1994) also revealed a positive association between job satisfaction and life satisfaction, highlighting the broader implications of job satisfaction.

Moreover, job satisfaction is not only crucial for personnel well-being but also impacts organizational effectiveness. Consequently, researchers have explored the job satisfaction of library personnel, including those in Information Technology (I.T.) roles. Despite the growing presence of I.T. workers in academic libraries, empirical studies on their job satisfaction are limited. For example, studies by Salanova et al. (2016) and Huang et al. (2017) focused on the job satisfaction of I.T. workers in academic libraries, but there remains a lack of understanding regarding the specific factors influencing their satisfaction. Taylor (2000) and Lim (2007) provided early insights into the job satisfaction of library I.T. workers, examining specific job tasks and qualifications.

This study seeks to fill this void by investigating the job satisfaction of IT workers in libraries and its connection to different background and work-related factors. These background variables encompass demographic and socioeconomic factors such as gender, race, age, education level, years of experience in the library field, and salary. Additionally, the study will explore specific work-related variables to better understand the factors contributing to job satisfaction among library I.T. workers, including tasks related to integrated library system management, network management, administration, and other computer applications.

Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction in Private University Settings

Employee performance is closely tied to motivation, a concept extensively studied in management theories since Frederick Taylor's "The Principles of Scientific Management" in 1911 and Henry Gantt's works on wages and profits in 1913. While traditional approaches like Taylor's "differential rate piece-work" and Gantt's "task and bonus wages" system have been debunked, contemporary management practices have progressed to comprehend and utilize motivation more effectively. Meyer and Becker (2004) offer a comprehensive definition of motivation as a set of internal and external forces driving work-related behaviors, influencing their form, direction, intensity, and duration.

Various management theories have been instrumental in understanding and addressing employee motivation. Maslow's hierarchy of needs delineates five levels of needs—psychological, safety, social, self-esteem, and self-actualization—forming the basis for motivating employees according to their level of need fulfillment (Samad, 2007). Locke and Latham (1990) introduced the goal-setting theory, emphasizing the importance of setting specific goals to maximize performance. This theory, rooted in the concept of self-efficacy, asserts that individuals perform best when they have a clear understanding of the behaviors required to achieve their goals.

Herzberg's two-factor theory further elucidates motivational factors, categorizing them into satisfiers and dissatisfiers. Intrinsic factors are associated with job satisfaction, while extrinsic factors contribute to dissatisfaction (Gagne, 2007). These motivational factors are often classified into intrinsic and extrinsic categories (Guzzo, 1979; Mitchell, 1982; Gagne, 2005). Meyer and Herscovitch (2001) define commitment as a binding force that ties an individual to a particular course of action relevant to a specific target. While commitment reflects the organization's responsiveness, job satisfaction is more influenced by specific job facets. Nonetheless, job satisfaction remains central to understanding employee motivation and organizational effectiveness.

Understanding and addressing work motivation and job satisfaction are paramount for enhancing employee performance and organizational success in private university settings. By recognizing and leveraging various motivational factors, organizations can cultivate a positive work environment conducive to employee satisfaction and productivity. This comprehensive approach is essential for developing strategies that enhance library staff motivation, improve organizational culture, and ultimately contribute to a more satisfied and productive library workforce.

Job satisfaction and organizational culture among employees in private Universities.

Organizational culture encompasses the longstanding beliefs, values, and norms within an institution, influencing how employees perceive their roles and interact with one another (Cameron & Quinn, 2015). A positive organizational culture fosters a supportive and engaging work environment, which can enhance job satisfaction, employee morale, and overall productivity (Denison, 2018).

Administrators play a critical role in shaping and maintaining organizational culture. A major objective of any organization is to maximize productivity, through the discharge of organization functions (Oyeniran & Irenoa, 2021). These roles are impacted by the leadership behaviors, decision-making processes, and interpersonal interactions set the tone for the workplace environment. Effective leaders align their behaviors with the organization's mission and values, which can have a profound impact on employee job satisfaction. When leaders exhibit behaviors that are congruent with the institution's values, they reinforce a sense of purpose and belonging among staff, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction (Schein, 2016).

Research indicates that leadership behaviors that support and reinforce a positive organizational culture are crucial for enhancing job satisfaction (Ostroff et al., 2015). For instance, transformational leadership, which involves inspiring and motivating employees to exceed expectations, has been shown to positively influence job satisfaction by fostering a culture of trust, respect, and encouragement (Bass & Riggio, 2016). Additionally, participative leadership, where leaders involve employees in decision-making processes, can enhance job satisfaction by making employees feel valued and empowered (Yukl, 2017).

Understanding the interplay between organizational culture, leadership behavior, and employee satisfaction is crucial for administrators seeking to improve workplace outcomes. A strong, positive organizational culture can mitigate stress and job burnout, contributing to higher job satisfaction and reduced turnover rates (Schneider et al., 2017). Conversely, a negative organizational culture, characterized by poor communication, lack of support, and misalignment with organizational values, can lead to dissatisfaction, decreased motivation, and higher turnover (Kuenzi & Schminke, 2017).

Empirical studies support the notion that organizational culture significantly affects job satisfaction. For example, a study by Chatman and O'Reilly (2016) found that employees who perceive their organizational culture as supportive and aligned with their personal values report higher job satisfaction. Similarly, Hartnell, Kinicki, Lambert, Fugate, and Doyle (2016) demonstrated that a positive organizational culture, characterized by innovation, support, and stability, is strongly associated with higher job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Impacts of organizational structure and culture on job satisfaction

Managing human resources effectively within organizations is a significant concern for HR managers and policymakers. To achieve satisfaction, organizations must ensure consistency across their structure, systems, people, culture, and alignment with strategy. This paper aims

to identify factors within organizational structure and culture that influence job satisfaction and stress through a comprehensive review of existing literature.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of organizational structure and culture in shaping job satisfaction. Organizational structure encompasses hierarchy, departmentalization, and centralization, which can influence how employees perceive their roles and responsibilities. For instance, a study by Bauer and Erdogan (2016) emphasized that a flatter organizational structure, which encourages more employee autonomy and involvement in decision-making processes, generally leads to higher job satisfaction. This is because employees feel more valued and empowered when they have a say in important decisions affecting their work.

Leadership and managerial practices are critical components of organizational culture that significantly impact job satisfaction. Effective leadership that promotes a positive organizational climate and supportive supervisory styles can enhance employee motivation and satisfaction. According to Johnson, Scholes, and Whittington (2018), transformational leadership, characterized by inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, is particularly effective in boosting job satisfaction as it fosters an environment of trust and respect.

Conversely, factors like centralization and limited participation in decision-making may negatively affect job satisfaction. Centralization can lead to a lack of autonomy and decreased employee morale, as decision-making is concentrated at the top levels of the organization, leaving little room for employee input. This can result in feelings of disenfranchisement and increased job stress. A study by Van de Voorde, Paauwe, and Van Veldhoven (2016) found that excessive centralization and bureaucratic structures are associated with lower job satisfaction and higher employee stress.

Managerial practices, such as communication, feedback, and recognition, also play a pivotal role in shaping organizational culture and employee satisfaction. Effective communication ensures that employees are well-informed about organizational goals and their roles within the organization, which enhances their sense of purpose and alignment with the organization's mission. Feedback and recognition, on the other hand, contribute to employees' perceived value and motivation. According to a study by Kim and Park (2017), regular and constructive supervisor feedback strongly correlates with higher job satisfaction and lower turnover intentions.

Another critical factor is the decision-making process within an organization. Participative decision-making, where employees are involved in the decision-making process, has increased job satisfaction. This inclusive approach enhances employees' sense of ownership and accountability and improves their commitment to organizational goals. Research by Sousa and Vala (2019) indicates that organizations implementing participative decision-making practices experience higher levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment among their employees.

Organizational climate, which refers to the shared perceptions of organizational policies, practices, and procedures, mediates the relationship between organizational structure and job satisfaction. A positive organizational climate that promotes fairness, support, and open communication can mitigate the negative effects of a rigid organizational structure. Schneider, González-Romá, Ostroff, and West (2017) highlight that a supportive organizational climate fosters a sense of belonging and well-being among employees, thereby enhancing job satisfaction.

Methodology

This study employed a survey descriptive research design. A preliminary test was undertaken to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire. 30 copies were administered to library personnel at Hezekiah Oluwasanmi Library in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. The Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to assess the reliability coefficient of every dimension within the questionnaire. The yielding reliability coefficients are 0.95% for Work Motivation, 0.6% for Organizational Culture, and 0.91% for Job Satisfaction. The research design is ex post facto, as the independent variables, Work Motivation and Organizational Culture, were not manipulated but rather observed as they naturally occurred. The dependent variable in this study is Job Satisfaction. The study population consists of 177 library personnel from private universities in the South West region of Nigeria. These private Universities are Babcock University, Covenant University, Bowen University, Lead City University, Adeleke University and Joseph Ayo Babalola University.

Research Instruments

The study utilized a questionnaire comprising three sections: A, B, and C. Section A focused on personal details such as marital status, job tenure, education level, religion, and monthly income. Section B contained 30 items assessing work motivation and organizational culture, while Section C comprised 20 items gauging job satisfaction.

The researcher utilized the Work Motivation Scale to assess the work motivation levels of the respondents. Items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not Important) to 5 (Absolutely Important). Example items included:

- i. Financial reward
- ii. High-technology devices for work
- iii. Childcare
- iv. Elder care plan
- v. Education benefit

The Organizational Culture Scale, adapted from Dunham and Castenda (1994), aimed to assess the organizational culture of library personnel. Items were rated on a 4-point Likert scale as follows: 1 = Almost Always, 2 = Often, 3 = Sometimes 4 = Rarely

Examples of items include:

- i. Change in the organization is viewed as a challenge or opportunity.
- ii. Organizational policies are regularly reviewed to assess effectiveness.
- iii. Rewards are given based on the performance of the recipient.
- iv. When issues arise, there is a readiness to tackle them.
- v. My boss appreciates ideas and promptly puts them into action.

Marcus Buckingham developed the Job Satisfaction Scale to assess the job satisfaction of library personnel. It comprises 20 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Dissatisfied) to 5 (Very Satisfied).

Data Collection and Analysis

177 questionnaires were distributed to library personnel across private universities in southwestern Nigeria. 150 were returned and considered for analysis, indicating a response rate of 84.745%. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistics, including percentages, means, and standard deviation, were employed to answer research inquiries, while inferential statistics, including correlation and regression analysis, were employed to test research hypotheses.

Among the 150 respondents, 80 (53%) were male, while 70 (46.7%) were female. Regarding educational qualifications, 25 (16.7%) possessed Senior Secondary School Certificate/General Certificate in Education (Ordinary level), 33 (22.0%) had completed Post-Secondary Education, and the majority, 90 (60%), were categorized as drop-outs in terms of religious beliefs. Regarding religious affiliation, 112 (74%) identified as Christians, and 38 (25.3%) as Muslims. Marital status varied, with 44 (29.3%) being single, 101 (67.3%) married, and 5 (3.3%) being widowed or separated. Additionally, 61 (4.07%) were classified as junior staff, while 89 (59.3%) were categorized as senior staff. Further details are provided in Tables 1, 2, and 3.

Table 1 shows the means of standard deviation scores of Motivation levels among library staff. Influence job satisfaction in private universities in South West Nigeria (Table of work motivation)

Table 1: Work motivation of respondents

S/N	Statement /Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Financial reward	150	4.33	1.10
2.	High-technology devices to work with	150	3.21	1.28
3.	Child care	150	2.92	1.23
4.	Elder care plans	150	3.00	1.24
5.	Education benefit	150	3.55	1.16
6.	Opportunity to do research with co-workers	150	3.09	1.29
7.	Developing new skills at work	150	3.16	1.32
8.	Frequency raise in pay	150	3.23	1.29
9.	A sense of adequacy on the job	150	3.47	1.01
10.	A complete fringe benefit package	150	3.84	1.34
11.	Opportunity for personal growth	150	4.05	1.18
12.	A sense of job security	150	4.17	1.08
13.	Performance-based competition	150	3.96	1.31
14.	Company car	150	3.21	1.20
15.	Flying first class	150	3.61	1.41
16.	Opportunity for creative thinking	150	3.94	1.25
17.	Honesty with co-workers	150	4.11	1.21

18	Cooperative relation/teamwork	150	3.99	1.31
19	A sense of security from physical harm	150	4.02	1.23
20	Flexible incentives	150	3.89	1.21
21	Alternative work schedules	150	3.68	1.41

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 displays mean and standard deviations for various items on the work motivation scale among private university library staff. The results show that the cumulative means, and standard deviation ($X = 76.43$, $SD = 26.06$) indicate that the library personnel have a positive view about work motivation of private university libraries in Nigeria. Responses to items on the work motivation scale echo this view. The majority of the respondents believe that "financial rewards" are viewed as a challenge and an opportunity" ($X = 4.33$, $SD = 1.10$). "Opportunity for personal growth" has ($X = 4.05$, $SD = 1.29$), "A service of job security" is ($X = 4.17$, $SD = 1.08$), and "honestly with co-workers" ($X = 4.11$, $SD = 1.21$). "A sense of security from physical harm" ($X = 4.02$, $SD = 1.23$), "flexible incentive" has ($X = 3.89$, $SD = 1.21$), "cooperative relation/teamwork" ($X = 3.99$, $SD = 1.31$), "opportunity for creative thinking" has ($X = 3.94$, $SD = 1.25$). "A complete fringe benefit package" ($X = 3.84$, $SD = 1.34$) and others like that in the table above show that work motivation is essential.

The high mean scores and relatively low standard deviations across various motivational factors suggest that private university library personnel in Nigeria perceive a positive work environment, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive motivational strategies to enhance employee satisfaction and productivity.

Table 2 shows the means of standard deviation scores of the organization culture scale of library personnel in private universities in southwestern Nigeria.

Table 2. Organizational culture of the respondent.

S/N	Statement/ Items	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	In my workplace, change is seen as both a challenge and an opportunity	150	3.06	.95
2.	To assess effectiveness, organizational policies are reviewed usually to assess effectiveness	150	2.82	.77
3.	Rewards are given out to suit the reference of the recipient	150	2.35	.84
4.	All levels of the organization welcome new ideas openly	150	2.55	.81
5.	When problems emerge, there is a willingness of fix them	150	2.87	.75
6.	My boss values new ideas and implements them quickly; performance evaluation in this organization measures an employee's adaptation to change	150	3.03	.91
7.	This organization evaluates employee adaptability to change in performance reviews	150	2.85	.81
8.	We readily implement mid-course adjustments as needed	150	2.54	.82

9.	There is a little variation in style of dress among employees	150	2.67	.79
10.	Our HR department is creative in finding new ways to attract top talent from diverse groups	150	2.70	.85
11.	Our strategic plan is evaluated once a year and reviewed as needed	150	2.27	.86
12.	We have always done it the way is a philosophy that describes my library responds new ideas	150	1.83	1.07
13.	Our products and services reflect the awareness of a diverse consumer base	150	2.95	.83
14.	His library's top executives exhibit innovation and approachability	150	2.97	.89
15.	Ugly trying to build or rebuild a "better mouse trap"	150	2.68	.90
	Total	150	40.14	12.85

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 presents the means and standard deviations of various items on the organizational culture scale for library personnel in private universities in South West Nigeria. The cumulative means and standard deviation ($X = 40.14$, $SD = 12.85$) suggest a favourable perception of organizational culture among library staff in Nigerian private universities. This view has also been expressed in the responses to the different items on your organizational culture scale. The majority of the respondents believe that "in my organization changes is viewed as a challenge an opportunity" ($X = 3.06$, $SD = .95$), "my boss values new ideas and implement them quickly" ($X = 3.03$, $SD = .91$), "we can do make "mid-course" correlation easily" ($X = 2.54$, $SD = .82$) "organizational policies are reviewed usually to assess effectiveness" ($X = 2.82$, $SD = .77$), "when problem emerge, there is willingness to fix them" ($X = 2.87$, $SD = .75$), performance evaluation in this organization measure and employee adaption to change ($X = 2.85$, $SD = .81$) and a host of other from the table shows that organization culture is good.

The positive mean scores and low standard deviations imply a supportive and adaptable organizational culture among private university library personnel in Southwest Nigeria, fostering innovation, problem-solving, and a willingness to embrace change, ultimately enhancing overall organizational effectiveness and employee satisfaction.

Table 3: Showing job satisfaction of library personnel respondents in Southwest Nigeria.

Table of job satisfaction

S/N	Statement /Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	On my present job, this is how I feel about	150	4.01	.68
2.	Being able to keep busy all the time	150	3.69	.84
3.	The chance to work on the job	150	3.34	1.19
4.	The competence of my supervisor in making the decision	150	3.19	1.08
5.	Being able to do things that do not go against my conscience	150	3.34	1.05
6.	The chance to do things for people	150	3.91	0.82
7.	The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	150	3.89	0.74
8.	My pay and the amount of work I do	150	2.62	1.39
9.	The freedom to use my judgement	150	2.63	1.29
10.	The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	150	2.49	1.30

11.	The working conditions	150	2.69	1.38
12.	The way co-workers get along with each other.	150	2.75	1.41
13.	The praise I get from doing a good job	150	3.29	1.19
14.	The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	150	3.48	1.10
15.	The chance to tell the people what to do	150	3.29	1.14
16.	The chances of advancement on this job	150	2.90	1.35
17.	The chance to do difference things in the community	150	2.90	1.35
18.	The chance to be somebody in the community	150	2.86	1.40
19.	The way my boss handle subordinates	150	3.13	1.43
20.	The way my job provides for steady employment	150	2.89	1.36
21.	The way library policies are put into practice	150	3.03	1.10
			66.47	24.25

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 presents the means and standard deviations of scores for various items on the job satisfaction scale among library personnel at a private university in South West Nigeria. The overall cumulative mean and standard deviation ($X = 66.47$, $SD = 24.25$) suggest high job satisfaction among these personnel. This sentiment is consistently echoed in their responses across the different items on the job satisfaction scale. The majority of the respondents believe that "on my present job, this is how I feel about" ($X = 401$, $SD = 68$). "The chance of advancements on the job" ($X = 2.90$, $SD = 1.35$), "the way my boss handles subordinates" ($X = 2.89$, $SD = 1.36$), "the way job provides for steady employment" ($X = 3.03$, $SD = 1.10$), the way library policies are put into practice ($X = 3.05$, $SD = 1.01$), "The chance to tell people what to do" ($X = 3.29$, $SD = 1.19$) "The feeling of accomplishment I got from the job" ($X = 3.48$, $SD = 1.10$), "The chance of work alone on the job" ($X = 3.34$, $SD = 1.19$), "being able to keep busy all the time" ($X = 3.69$, $SD = .84$), These and many others from the above table shows that job satisfaction among private university workers is high hence, library workers in private university are satisfied with it. The high mean scores and low standard deviations indicate strong job satisfaction among private university library personnel in Southwest Nigeria. This suggests a conducive work environment, fostering employee contentment, productivity, and retention, contributing to overall organizational success and stability.

Table 4 illustrates the correlation matrix depicting the interrelationship between work motivation, organizational culture, and job satisfaction among library personnel.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Job Satisfaction	P	Rank
Work Motivation	150	76.43	14.639	0.197	.016	Sig.
Organizational Culture	150	40.127	7.087	0.166	0.27	Sig.
Job Satisfaction	150	66.44	15.8447	1.000		

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction from the table 1, The means & Standard deviation of jobs satisfaction are $X = 66.44$, $SD = 15.8447$. Testing the proposed hypothesis 2 reveals a significant correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction ($r = 0.197$, $P < 0.05$), leading to the rejection of the stated hypothesis 1.

Hypothesis 2: posits that there is no substantial correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction within library staff. According to Table 1, the mean and standard deviation for organizational culture are calculated as ($X = 66.44$, $SD = 15.84447$). However, upon conducting a test for Hypothesis 3, it is evident that there exists a significant correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction ($r = 0.166$, $p < 0.05$).

Therefore, the stated hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 3: The combination of work motivation and organizational culture has no significant relationship with job satisfaction. To test this hypothesis, the data were subjected to multiple regression analysis. The results are expressed in Tables 5 & 6. There will be no joint effect of independent variables (work motivation and organizational culture) on job satisfaction.

Table 5: Summary of multiple regression analysis showing the relationship between independent variables (work motivation and organizational culture) and dependent variable (job satisfaction of library personnel).

Model	R	RSquare	Adjusted	Std. Error
1	405a	164	147	14.6320

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 6: Showing analysis of variance showing the relationship between work motivation, organizational culture and job satisfaction of the library personnel

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig (P)
Regression	6149.170	3	2049.723	9.574	0000
Residual	31257.904	146	214.095		
Total	37407.073	149			

Source: Field Survey, 2023

(a) Predictor (constant) work motivation and organizational culture

(b) Dependent variable (job satisfaction) $P < 0.05$

The data in the table shows that the independent variable work motivation and organizational culture have a significant multiple correlation with job satisfaction ($R = 405$, $P < 0.05$). The data also shows that the coefficient of determination R^2 of 164 indicates that the independent variable explains 16.4% of the variance in the dependent variable job satisfaction) the remaining 84.6% may be due to other factors not considered in the study. The data in the table indicates that the independent variable significantly influences job satisfaction $F = 9.574$, $DF = 3, 146$, $P < 0.05$).

The table indicates that the independent variable significantly influences job satisfaction $F = 9.574$, $DF = 3, 146$, $P < 0.05$).

Table 7: Multiple combinations of independent variables (work motivation and organizational culture) serve as the prediction in the independent variables of (job satisfaction)

Table 7 shows the relative contribution of work motivation and organizational culture to predicting the job satisfaction of library personnel in private university libraries.

Model	B	SE(B)	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	106.789	13.427		7.954	0.000
Work Motivation	0.198	0.084	0.184	2.366	0.019
Organizational Culture	0.541	0.173	0.242	3.128	.002

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The result above shows the relative contribution of each independent variable to the dependent work motivation ($B = 169$, $P < 0.05$). Organizational culture was found significant because they all contributed to job satisfaction.

Discussion of the findings

The findings of this study reveal a significant positive correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction, suggesting that higher levels of work motivation are associated with higher levels of job satisfaction and vice versa. This aligns with recent research that describes motivation as the driving force behind actions, leading to enhanced staff performance (Deci et al., 2017). It is important to note that a lack of motivation can decrease productivity. Hence, respondents demonstrate a favourable correlation between their work motivation and satisfaction with their job. However, these findings contradict earlier research that suggested a negative relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction, where high job satisfaction led to decreased work motivation (Zheng et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the study indicates a significant positive association between organizational culture and job satisfaction among library personnel in private universities in Southwest Nigeria. This suggests that higher levels of organizational culture are linked to higher levels of job satisfaction. This finding aligns with research emphasizing the importance of creating an organizational culture supporting teamwork and rewarding employees who exhibit a positive attitude towards team-based rewards (Jiang & Chen, 2018). This indicates a positive relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction among respondents.

While the study identifies a positive correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction, it also highlights conflicting findings regarding the impact of employee suggestion programs and organizational culture on job satisfaction. These results underscore the complexity of factors influencing job satisfaction and the need for further research to understand the underlying mechanisms fully. The study reveals a notable correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction, where a supportive and inclusive culture enhances job satisfaction (Nguyen et al., 2020).

In scenarios where one team member shoulders the bulk of the workload but receives the same recognition as the entire team, negativity toward teamwork can develop, negatively impacting future participation and job satisfaction (Tsai, 2011). This highlights the adverse relationship between perceived inequities in organizational culture and job satisfaction among respondents.

Similarly, the study finds a significant positive association between work motivation and job satisfaction. High motivation levels often coincide with high job satisfaction, while reduced motivation corresponds with lower job satisfaction. This aligns with recent studies on the factors influencing and perpetuating human behaviour towards committed objectives (Ryan & Deci, 2019). Managers' understanding of motivation as a resource that requires periodic replenishment is crucial. Moreover, motivation is highlighted as a managerial tool for tailoring job assignments and rewards to align with employees' preferences, indicating a positive correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction.

However, these findings contrast with earlier research advocating for Employee Suggestion Programs (ESPs) to enhance employee involvement in decision-making processes. While ESPs are touted for tapping into employees' intelligence and resourcefulness, yielding economic benefits, some studies found an inverse correlation between work motivation and job satisfaction (Aguinis et al., 2019). When job satisfaction levels are elevated, work motivation can sometimes decrease, highlighting the intricate association between these two factors.

Furthermore, the study reveals a significant positive link between organizational culture and job satisfaction among library personnel in private universities in Southwest Nigeria. A strong organizational culture often coincides with higher job satisfaction levels. This finding corroborates the assertion that designing organizational cultures supporting and rewarding employees can foster positive job satisfaction outcomes (Cameron & Quinn, 2019). This

emphasizes the importance of organizational culture in shaping employee perceptions and satisfaction levels within the workplace.

Studies on pay-for-performance have emphasized the connection between organizational culture and job satisfaction among library personnel, noting a positive correlation (Gerhart & Fang, 2015). Several variables influencing performance, including job agency characteristics, attitudes towards merit pay, organizational trust and commitment, the importance of monetary rewards, the link between pay and performance, and the fairness of the pay system, were identified as significant factors.

The findings of this study reveal a significant inverse correlation between perceived inequities in organizational culture and job satisfaction. Specifically, job satisfaction tends to be low when organizational culture is perceived to be unfair. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that situations where team members are rewarded collectively for a job well done, despite one member contributing significantly more, may lead to feelings of unfairness and dissatisfaction among team members (Demircioglu & Audretsch, 2017). Consequently, individuals who perceive such inequities may develop negative perceptions towards teamwork, impacting their job satisfaction negatively.

The connection between organizational culture and job satisfaction is complex and diverse. While there is evidence supporting a positive correlation between the two, certain organizational dynamics, such as inequitable reward systems, can negatively impact job satisfaction. Organizations must consider these factors when designing performance management strategies and incentive programs to ensure alignment with organizational culture and employee satisfaction.

Conclusion

In managing human resources within Nigerian universities, the primary aim should be to enhance work motivation and organizational commitment. This involves recognizing the importance of job satisfaction and ensuring that it addresses the diverse needs of staff. Integrating work motivation with organizational culture is crucial, especially for effectively administering library workers in private universities to ensure they are satisfied with their jobs. Effective administration must continually understand and apply appropriate theories to improve job satisfaction while also addressing the fundamental needs of the staff. By doing so, private universities can create a more motivated and committed workforce, leading to better overall performance.

Recommendations

1. Private universities ought to determine the most suitable approach for enhancing productivity among their workforce.
2. Implementing participative management can foster a sense of belonging among employees, leading to improved productivity and quality in private university administration.
3. Enhancing the rewards system in private universities is imperative, as studies indicate that some staff members are dissatisfied with the current system. Introducing bonuses and cash awards can effectively boost staff motivation and job satisfaction.

References

- Aguinis, H., Gottfredson, R. K., & Joo, H. (2016). Best-practice recommendations for defining, identifying, and handling outliers. *Organizational Research Methods, 16*(2), 270-301.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2016). *Transformational Leadership*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Bauer, T., & Erdogan, B. (2016). *Organizational Behavior*. New York, NY: OpenStax.
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2015). *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture: Based on the Competing Values Framework*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2019). *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture: Based on the Competing Values Framework*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Chatman, J. A., & O'Reilly, C. A. (2016). Paradigm lost: Reinvigorating the study of organizational culture. *Research in Organizational Behavior, pp. 36*, 199–224.
- Deci, E. L., Olafsen, A. H., & Ryan, R. M. (2017). Self-determination theory in work organizations: The state of science. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior, 4*, 19-43.
- Demircioglu, M. A., & Audretsch, D. B. (2017). Conditions for innovation in public sector organizations. *Research Policy, 46*(9), 1681-1691.
- Denison, D. R. (2018). *Corporate Culture and Organizational Effectiveness*. New York, NY: Wiley.
- Gagne, M. (2007). The role of autonomy support and autonomy orientation in prosocial behaviour engagement. *Motivation and Emotion, pp. 27*, 199–223.
- Gagne, M. (2005). The role of autonomy support and autonomy orientation in prosocial behaviour engagement. *Motivation and Emotion, pp. 27*, 199–223.
- Gerhart, B., & Fang, M. (2015). Pay for (individual) performance: Issues, claims, evidence, and the role of sorting effects. *Human Resource Management Review, 25*(1), 53-66.
- Gupta, N., & Shaw, J. D. (2018). Employee compensation: The neglected area of HRM research. *Human Resource Management Review, 18*(1), 1–4.
- Huang, M. H., Yang, C. L., & Su, J. G. (2017). The link between work environment and job satisfaction: Evidence from IT workers in Taiwan. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict, 21*(2), 1-15.
- Johnson, G., Scholes, K., & Whittington, R. (2018). *Exploring Corporate Strategy: Text and Cases*. London: Pearson Education.
- Judge, T. A., & Watanabe, S. (1994). Individual differences in the nature of the relationship between job and life satisfaction. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 67*(2), 101-107.
- Jiang, K., & Chen, Y. (2018). Team rewards and teamwork in organizations: An analysis of the multidimensional framework. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 39*(7), 942-954.
- Kim, S., & Park, S. (2017). Leadership, communication, and employee outcomes: Testing a multilevel mediating model. *Human Resource Management Journal, 27*(2), 209-225.
- Kuenzi, M., & Schminke, M. (2017). Assembling fragments into a lens: A review, critique, and proposed research agenda for the organizational work climate literature. *Journal of Management, 35*(3), 634-717.
- Landry, R. (2020). Exploring the relationship between job satisfaction and overall life satisfaction in public library workers. *Library Quarterly, 90*(1), 45–61.
- Lim, S. (2007). Library I.T. workers: Job satisfaction and task analysis. *Journal of Library Administration, 46*(2), 31–46.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (1990). *A Theory of Goal Setting and Task Performance*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.

- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, pp. 50, 370–396.
- Meyer, J. P., & Becker, T. E. (2004). Employee commitment and motivation: A conceptual analysis and integrative model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(6), 991-1007.
- Meyer, J. P., & Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the workplace: Toward a general model. *Human Resource Management Review*, 11(3), 299–326.
- Nguyen, L. T., Nguyen, H. Q., & Vu, T. A. (2020). The relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction: Evidence from Vietnam. *Management Review Quarterly*, 70(4), 583-600.
- Ostroff, C., Kinicki, A. J., & Tamkins, M. M. (2015). Organizational culture and climate. In C. L. Cooper (Ed.), *The Handbook of Work and Health Psychology* (pp. 565-593). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- Oyeniran, K. G., & Irenea, K. O. (2021). Organizational Constraints, Work Artitude and Job Performance of Librarians in Selected Public University Libraries in Nigeria. *Niger Delta Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(1), 1–11. <https://works.bepress.com/kennirenoa/9/>
- Parker, S. K., Bindl, U. K., & Strauss, K. (2017). Making things happen: A model of proactive motivation. *Journal of Management*, 36(4), 827-856.
- Posthuma, R. A., Campion, M. C., & Campion, M. A. (2018). A taxonomy of work team diversity: Integrating a decade of research. *Journal of Management*, 34(5), 1293-1330.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2019). Brick by brick: The origins, development, and future of self-determination theory. In R. M. Ryan (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Human Motivation* (pp. 417-447). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Salanova, M., Llorens, S., & Cifre, E. (2016). The dark side of technologies: Technostress among users of information and communication technologies. *International Journal of Psychology*, 51(4), 224-232.
- Samad, S. (2007). Assessing the effects of job satisfaction and psychological contract on organizational commitment among employees in Malaysia. *The Business Review*, 7(2), 72–81.
- Schein, E. H. (2016). *Organizational Culture and Leadership*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Schaufeli, W. B. (2018). Applying the job demands-resources model: A 'how to' guide to measuring and tackling work engagement and burnout. *Organizational Dynamics*, 46(2), 120-132.
- Schneider, B., González-Romá, V., Ostroff, C., & West, M. A. (2017). Organizational climate and culture: Reflections on the history of the constructs in the *Journal of Applied Psychology*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(3), 468-482.
- Sousa, S. D., & Vala, J. (2019). Perceived justice in leader-follower relationships. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 30(5), 101311.
- Taylor, F. W. (1911). *The Principles of Scientific Management*. New York, NY: Harper & Brothers.
- Tsai, Y. (2011). Relationship between organizational culture, leadership behavior and job satisfaction. *BMC Health Services Research*, 11, 98.
- Van de Voorde, K., Paauwe, J., & Van Veldhoven, M. (2016). Employee well-being and the HRM-organizational performance relationship: A review of quantitative studies. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 14(4), 391-407.
- Van der Voet, J., Kuipers, B. S., & Groeneveld, S. (2016). Implementing change in public organizations: The relationship between leadership and affective commitment to change in a public sector context. *Public Management Review*, 18(6), 842-865.

- Warr, P., & Inceoglu, I. (2018). Work orientations, well-being and job content of self-employed and employed professionals. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, 23*(3), 338-352.
- Yukl, G. (2017). *Leadership in Organizations*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Zheng, X., Wu, H., Eisenberger, R., Shore, L., Tetrick, L., & Buffardi, L. (2016). Newcomer leader-member exchange: The contribution of anticipated organizational support. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 89*